
Study the Effect of Alcoholic Flaxseed Extract on Naphthalene-induced Hemolytic Anemia in Syrian Hamster

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Abstract The study aimed to experiment the effect of alcoholic flaxseed extract on hemolytic anemia caused by naphthalene in the Syrian hamster and to determine some of the resulting hematological and histological changes. The study was conducted on 32 hamsters in four equal groups, the first group animals (control) were dosed with physiological solution NaCl (at a concentration of 0.9%), the second group was administered only with alcoholic flax seed extract (30 mg / 100 g) at a once-daily dose for three Weeks, the third group was also dosed with naphthalene (100 mg / 100 g) daily for three weeks, while the fourth group was dosed with the alcohol extract of flaxseed and naphthalene simultaneously and the same amount from previous doses and the duration of treatment. The results of the hematological study showed a significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) in the number of erythrocytes, hemoglobin and hematocrit values in the blood of the third group compared with the control group. A significant increase ($P < 0.001$) was observed for hematological parameters in the blood of the fourth group compared to the third group. The results of the histological study of the spleen of group III animals showed a clear appearance of hemolysis in the red pulp and congestion of the white pulp, while the improvement was evident with signs of recovery and there is no deposition of hemosdrin in the tissues of the spleen from animals that were detected by extracting alcoholic from flaxseed and naphthalene together. The results showed the great importance of flaxseed and its extracts as a natural substance in preventing hemolytic anemia with naphthalene.

Keywords hamsters, spleen, naphthalene, hemolytic anemia, flaxseed alcoholic extract

Introduction

Medicinal plants play an important role in the management of different diseases [1]. Plant products are known to show the protective effects by scavenging free radicals and modulating antioxidant defense system. Flax is a medicinal plant widely spread in various countries of the world where it grows in the deep moist soil rich in sand, silt and mud, and reaches a height of about 60 cm, its flowers are blue in color with golden seeds or yellow and belongs to the linen family linaceae where flaxseed seeds known Flaxseed (*Linum usitatissimum*) contains antioxidant compounds and some components that improve the body's various functions such as Lignan, phenolic acid, flavonoids, Phenylpropanoid glucosoids and Tannin [2-3]. Healthy properties are related to anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, anti-carcinogenic activities and to the lowering of cholesterol, the decrease of cardiovascular disease and the prevention of diabetes. However, in state of functional properties, flaxseed contains low quantities of adverse healthy compounds such as cadmium, cyanogenic glycosides, inhibitors of trypsin that are

commonly removed through thermal and mechanical processes, including cooking in microwaves, autoclaving and boiling [4]. Naphthalene is a bicyclic aromatic hydrocarbon that is widely used in moth repellents, lavatory scent discs and soil fumigants. It is also used in the manufacturing of naphthylamines, anthranilic and phthalic acids, and synthetic resins [5]. The toxicity induced by naphthalene cause oxidative damage. It has been demonstrated that naphthalene exposure results in elevated levels of serum and liver lipid peroxides, and decreased hepatic selenium-dependent glutathione peroxidase activity [6]. Naphthalene exposure is associated with the development of haemolytic anaemia in humans and rats. Naphthalene has also been shown to induce oxidative stress as evidenced by hepatic and brain lipid peroxidation, glutathione (GSH) depletion, DNA single strand breaks and membrane microviscosity, and excretion of urinary lipid metabolites in rats. Thus, the toxicity of naphthalene is at least in part related to free radicals and free radical-mediated oxidative stress [7].

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Flaxseed Extract

A flaxseed extract was prepared according to the method of Zhang & Wang [8].

Flaxseeds (500 g) were ground in a coffee grinder to obtain a fine powder, then the fine powder of flaxseeds was defatted by blending the ground material with hexane (1: 6, w/v) for 12 h at 25 °C. The defatted flaxseed powder was air dried for 12 h. Two hundred grams of this powder was blended with a 1.2 L mixture solvent of ethanol and water (7: 3, v/v) for 24 h at room temperature. The extract (polyphenol compounds) was filtered, and then concentrated at 50 °C by a rotary evaporator (Buch, Model 462, Germany) at 90 rpm. Light yellow syrup was obtained. The syrup was dissolved in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) at a concentration of 30 mg/0.25 mL.

Animal Treatment

The current study was carried out on 32 male Syrian hamsters aged 3-4 months, weight ranges between 80-110g, the animals were obtained from a commercial source, animals were placed in the laboratory for 2-3 weeks before starting the experiment in order to adapt to its appropriate conditions such as light and temperature (18-20 ° C), they were also provided with adequate food daily.

The experiment animals were divided into four equal groups, (8 animals per group):

Group I (control): Animals were treated daily for a period of / 21 / days with (0.05 ml) of physiological solution (0.9%).

Group II: Animals were orally administered with an alcoholic extract of flaxseed by 30 mg / 100 g for 21 days.

Group III: Animals were orally administered with naphthalene (dose amount 100 mg / 100 g) daily for a period of three weeks. Dosages were solved (separately) with corn oil before the dose.

Group IV: Animals were orally administered daily for three weeks in two doses, the first with an alcoholic extract of flaxseed (dose of 30 mg / 100 g) and the second with naphthalene (dose of 100 mg / 100 g).

Collect Blood and Spleen Samples

After completing the experiment, the animals were anesthetized and drawn blood directly by stabbing the heart with a 5 ml injection needle, placed in 5 ml test tubes, the abdomen was opened and the spleen was removed from the four animal groups, stored separately in 50-ml plastic containers containing formalin at a concentration of 10 % even histological study.

Hematological Analysis

Hematological parameters such as red blood cell count, hemoglobin and hematocrit were determined using a hemocytometer segment and calculated using the method of Wilkinson [9].

Histological Study

The spleen of the experimental animals was prepared and treated with commercial alcohol, absolute alcohol and xylene, then fixed with paraffin molds. The tissue sections were made with a thickness of (5) microns using the

tissue sector (Meditome A 550), then they were treated with alcohol and xylene solutions in preparation to be stained with hematoxylin-eosin according to the method of Maity [10]. Then, the tissue sections were studied using a light microscope equipped with a digital camera and connected to a computer with the intention of identifying the tissue changes occurring in the spleen of hamsters under the influence of dosage with the alcohol extract of flaxseed and naphthalene.

Statistical Analysis

The results of the calibration of the level of hematological parameters RBC, Hb, HTC were expressed in this study by the adoption of concentrations of measurement averages \pm the error of deviation from the mean for each blood criterion for experimental animals in each group. Dunnett and Duncan were tested within the SPSS statistical program, and a value of $P < 0.05$ was adopted as a lower statistic indication of changes in the parameters of blood parameters.

Results

The effect of alcoholic extract of flaxseed and naphthalene on the red blood cell count

The results of the mean values of the erythrocytes in the blood of experimental groups animals showed some changes in the table 1. However, it was not significant in the blood of animals of the second group doses with alcoholic extract of flaxseed (30mg/100g) compared to the blood of the animals of the control group, the differences were significant ($P < 0.001$) in the mean of their numbers between the animals of the two control groups and the second compared with the mean of their numbers in the blood of hamsters in the third group, Where hemolysis was evident with the effect of naphthalene (doses 100mg/100g). The differences between the mean numbers of erythrocytes between the first (control) group and fourth group animals that were simultaneously dosed with the alcohol extract of flaxseed with naphthalene were insignificant due to the effect of flaxseed components on reducing the hematopoies caused by the use of naphthalene (100mg/100g). However, a significant increase ($P < 0.001$) was observed with respect to the average number of erythrocytes in the blood of group IV animals compared to their mean in the blood of group III-dose animals with naphthalene only, and this may also be due to the effect of flax seed components on reducing the negative effect of naphthalene

The effect of alcoholic extract of flaxseed and naphthalene on the hemoglobin level

The results in Table 1 showed the values of mean hemoglobin and its mean concentrations in the four experimental groups, but the differences were not significant between their mean in the blood of the control group hamsters and their mean in the blood of second group hamsters (alcohol extract of flaxseed 30 mg/100g), where the values generally converged with one another, the dose of naphthalene 100 mg /100g resulted in a significant decrease in $P < 0.001$ of the mean hemoglobin concentration in the blood of the third group compared with their mean in the blood of the control and second group animals, However, the differences were not significant by comparing their averages between the animals of the fourth group dose with the alcoholic extract of flaxseed and naphthalene together with their means in the control group, and a significant rise in $P < 0.001$ was observed for the mean hemoglobin concentration in the blood of the fourth group animals compared with the average concentration in the blood of the third group animals which was administered with naphthalene only.

The effect of alcoholic extract of flaxseed and naphthalene on hematocrit

Table 1 showed the mean values of hematocrit in the blood of experimental and control groups of animals, non-significant differences between their mean in hamster blood in the second group treated with alcoholic extract of flaxseed compared with the control group, However, the differences were significant, and a significant decrease in $P < 0.001$ was observed for the mean hematocrit values after naphthalene dose 100mg/100g compared with the control group, Where the values reached about (29.70) after it was (39.08) in the control group, The differences were also significant $P < 0.001$ in the hematocrit averages between the blood of the hamsters of the second experimental group and the blood of the hamsters of the third experimental group, where the values decreased to (29.70) after their value

in the second group which was (36.38). The differences were also significant between the hematocrit averages in the fourth group dose with the alcohol extract of flaxseed and naphthalene together compared with the third group., Where a significant rise in $P < 0.05$ was observed while exploring values in the fourth group represented by a value of (35.50) after it was (29.70) in the third group administered with naphthalene only, as for the comparison of the hematocrit average values of the fourth group with the hematocrit average values of the control group, the difference was not significant, and these changes in the values are due to a decrease in the numbers of red blood cells due to hemolysis under the influence of naphthalene and limiting its effect using flaxseed on the other hand.

Table 1: Compare the average numbers of erythrocytes, hematocrit, and hemoglobin in the blood of experimental groups of animals that were dose with either flax seed extract (30 mg/100 g), or with naphthalene (100 mg/100 g), or flaxseed + naphthalene (100 mg/100 g)

Experimental groups	Red blood cell count million / mm ³	Hemoglobin g/dL	Hematocrit %
Control (physiological solution)	6.7±0.33	14.24±0.83	39.08±2.91
Alcoholic Flaxseed Extract (30 mg / 100 g)	6.44±1.21	14.36±0.79	36.38±5.44
Statistical significance	0.891	0.984	0.440
Naphthalene (100 mg / 100 g)	3.1±0.32	8.62±0.49	29.70±0.43
Statistical significance	0.000***	0.000***	0.001
Statistical significance between the second and third groups	0.000***	0.000***	0.014
Alcoholic extract of flaxseed + naphthalene	6.17±0.48	14.65±0.20	35.50±1.23
Statistical significance	0.571	0.685	0.274
Statistical significance between the third and fourth groups	0.000***	0.000***	0.045

Figure 1: Average erythrocyte numbers in experimental groups

Figure 2: Averages of hemoglobin concentration in experimental groups

Figure 3: Averages of Hematocrit concentration in experimental groups

The effect of alcoholic flaxseed extract on hamster spleen tissue

The results of the histological study of the spleen of the second experimental group showed the clarity of the red and white pulp, which is similar to the structure of the animal of the control group. And there were no signs of congestion or infiltration with signs of tissue alterations in the structure of the spleen due to animal dosing with the alcoholic extract of flaxseed.

The Effect of naphthalene dosage on hamster spleen tissue

The results of the current study showed some changes in the structure of spleen tissue of the third group animals that were dosed with naphthalene only. Manifested with severe congestion, necrosis and deposition of hemosdrin, with hemolysis in the red pulp, and hyperplasia of lymph white pulp.

The effect of simultaneous dosage of both flaxseed extract and naphthalene on the spleen tissue of hamsters

The results of the histological study of the spleen of the fourth group animals, which were dosed in daily doses of the alcohol extract of flaxseed and naphthalene seeds, showed a clear improvement in their histological evidence compared to the third group dosed only with naphthalene, where slight congestion in the red pulp was observed and there were no signs of hemosdrin.

Figure 4: Spleen animal experimental groups. a) Control, b) Alcoholic Flaxseed Extract (30 mg/100 g). It shows red pulp and white pulp naturally. c) Naphthalene (100 mg/100 g), shows Necrosis, hemosdrin deposition. d) Alcoholic extract of flaxseed + naphthalene, Appears Mild congestion with red pulp

Discussion

The results of Table 1 showed that the second group dosed with flaxseed extract only, which showed an insignificant rise in both the number of erythrocytes (RBC) and hemoglobin values (Hg) and hematocrit (HTC) consistent with the results of a study[11-12].

The results of Table 1 showed a significant decrease in the number of erythrocytes and hemoglobin and hematocrit values in group III dose with naphthalene. The results of the current study are consistent with the results of other studies and researches that have shown that exposure to naphthalene is linked to cellular toxicity and promotes the production of free radicals and causes hemolysis and reduction of hemoglobin levels after accidentally swallowing two dry naphthalene balls in persons aged 14-22 [13-16], also occurs Hemolytic anemia in mice and rabbits after dosing with different doses of naphthalene [17-18]. This is confirmed by the results of the current tissue study,

which showed that hamster dosing with naphthalene led to clear tissue changes in the spleen of the third experimental group and this is consistent with the results of other studies and researches where the effect of naphthalene is similar to the effect of sodium arsenic or Cadmium, lead acetate and the damage was manifested by the expansion of the white pulp and necrosis of the red pulp and deposition of hemosdrin [19-23].

This may be caused by the addition of naphthalene as doses to the hamster. This substance enters the blood and interacts with lipid cellular membranes of red blood cells and stimulates the formation of the Reactive oxygen species (ROS), which may lead to changes in the antioxidant system in the red blood cells and cause oxidative damage to the membrane thus causes hemolysis. This may be caused by the addition of naphthalene as doses to the hamster. This substance enters the blood and interacts with lipid cellular membranes of red blood cells and stimulates the formation of the Reactive oxygen species ROS, which may lead to changes in the antioxidant system in the red blood cells and cause oxidative damage to the membrane thus causes hemolysis [24-26] as naphthalene metabolizes into several metabolic products such as 1,2-Epoxy or quinones and the possibility of diol-epoxides [27].

Also the results showed in Table 1 a significant increase in blood parameters in the fourth group doses of alcoholic extract of flaxseed and naphthalene together through which it was shown its protective role in protecting against the dissolution of blood caused by naphthalene by containing phenolic compounds and this is consistent with the results of other researches and studies that have proven Several plant extracts rich in flavonoids, phenolic acids and alkalis act as antioxidants and increase red blood cell resistance against oxidative stress and protect them from dissolution in mice [28-30] The results of the histological study are consistent with other studies and researches that show that the effect of several effective medicinal plants containing alpha-linolenic acid or flavonoids may have an effective protective effect in protecting the tissue structure of the spleen or kidney against cellular stress factors induced by toxic substances by reducing the manifestations of oxidative stress and necrosis Cellular and the appearance of mild congestion red pulp [31-34]. This may be because flaxseed extract contains antioxidant compounds such as phenols and contains a high percentage of omega-3 as it inhibits fat peroxide and prevents protein oxidation and depletion of glutathione and reduces damage to the cell membrane structure [35-37].

Conclusion

Alcoholic flaxseed extract has a protective effect against hemolytic anemia and the harmful effects of naphthalene and this effect is dose dependent.

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